

Elucidating the Groundwater Regime from Geoelectric Survey within Institute of Technology, Kwara State Polytechnic Ilorin, North central Nigeria

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Abstract

A geoelectric survey involving Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) was carried out within the premises of the Institute of Technology, Kwara State Polytechnic Ilorin, north central Nigeria with the aim of determining the viable aquiferous zones in understanding the groundwater regime within the institute. Ten (10) VES were carried out using Schlumberger electrode array with half current spacing of 70m. The VES data generated was processed and interpreted using the partial curve matching method and computer iteration techniques. The interpreted field data revealed 5-6layered units which include the topsoil, laterite, clayey sand, weathered basement, basement and fresh bedrock with resistivity and thickness ranging from 72.4-753 Ωm with a thickness of 0.5- 2.05 m, 74.9-911 Ωm with thickness of 0.983 -3.54 m, 18.9-406 Ωm with thickness of about 3.07-19.6 m , 21.7-379 Ωm ; thickness of 5.3-44.5 m, 92.9-7521 Ωm ; thickness of about 11.4 -87.4m and 70.5 to 70798 Ωm with an indefinite thickness. The HA curve type is characterised by five layers while KH and KHA curves delineate six lithologic units. On the other hand, four lithologic units were observed on the QHA and KHA-type curves. Of all the lithologic units identified in the study area, only the weathered basement is adjudged to be the aquiferous layers which are of hydrogeologic significance. It is expected that areas with thickness (>25 m) weathered layers could be considered satisfactory for groundwater development. However, the basement usually possesses good groundwater potential due to enhanced porosity especially when its thickness is greater than 10 m.

Keywords: Aquifers, Geoelectric parameters, Groundwater exploration, Groundwater potential, Vertical Electrical Sounding

1.0 Introduction

Groundwater plays a key role in human existence because of its usefulness for domestic, agricultural and industrial activities. Despite this, there is minimal quantitative data on groundwater resources on the landmass, with groundwater storage capacity being subsequently precluded from freshwater accessibility appraisal reports [1]. Human effort has been directed at solving groundwater scarcity in a crystalline basement rock environment, through the identification of joints, cracks, fractures, faults, and weathered materials that may exhibit favourable disposition to groundwater accumulation for water sustainability [2]. While considering groundwater resources in areas lining oceans, coastal aquifers are a vital source of freshwater [3]. Freshwater stored in coastal aquifers is particularly

susceptible to degradation due to its proximity to salty seawater, as well as the higher population densities of coastal zones that lead to intensive water demand [4]. [5] argued that water availability is the bedrock of human development and monitoring its state of dynamism is a fundamental requirement for planning and management especially in Northern Nigeria. Increasing population and water scarcity have raised the importance of groundwater zones, as they are a major source of freshwater. Locating potential groundwater targets is becoming more convenient and cost-effective with the advent of a number of geophysical studies. Geophysics based groundwater exploration has made it feasible to explore areas with limited human access, because of the wide visual range, short time cycle, and

increasing spatial resolution. Groundwater occurrence in Precambrian basement terrain is hosted within zones of weathering and fracturing, which are often are not continuous in vertical and lateral extent [6]. Most groundwater projects recorded in basement complex aquifers have revealed geophysical survey as a compulsory prerequisite to any successful water well drilling project [7]. The electrical resistivity method involving the vertical electrical sounding (VES) technique is extensively gaining application in environmental, groundwater and engineering geophysical investigations [8]. Groundwater abstraction in the study area is mainly from shallow hand dug wells which are perched in nature and dry out during the dry season. Apart from drying out during the dry season, the water supplies from these shallow wells have not been

able to meet the growing population of the area. Several deep wells (boreholes) drilled within the institute have failed because of lack of geophysical survey, hence the need for this research. The aim of this study is to carry out a geophysical investigation into groundwater prospect within the study area by determining aquifers parameters from the interpreted VES data.

2.0 Materials and Method

2.1 The Study Area

The study area is located in Ilorin west within latitude 08°33'21" to 08°33'20.6"N, and longitude 004°38'07.0" to 004°38'09.6"E (Figure 1) covering an area of 200m². The area is accessible through General Hospital and Bamas Hotel Roads in temperature and the pressure resulting in features like joints, faults and folds [9]. Such fractures are those that influence the groundwater in crystalline rocks especially, if they exist at depth and are overlaid by a thick superficial cover known as overburden. It is composed subsurface lithology which comprises weathered, slightly weathered and fresh crystalline basement rocks. Gneiss complex one of the oldest rocks in the region is comprised of biotite-hornblende gneiss coupled with amphibolites this underlies more than half of the region [10]. Other components of the old gneiss complex include porphyritic granite.

Figure 1: Location Map of the Study Area

Figure 2: Location Map of the Study Area Showing VES Points

2.2 Geology of the Study Area

Geologically, the area belongs to the southwestern Nigeria Precambrian Basement Complex. Locally, the study area is underlain by Migmatite-gneiss complex (Figure 3). These rocks were emplaced in Precambrian times and have been subjected to tectonic activities characterized by large changes

Figure 3: Geology Map of the Study Area [11].

2.3 Geophysical survey

The materials used for this study includes but not limited to ohmega resistivity meter (DDC-8), electrodes, cables, tape, global positioning system, geologic hammer, record book, umbrella and power source.

2.3.1 Field Procedure

Geophysical investigations were carried out in order to locate areas of high groundwater potential characterized with thick weathered and fractures zones. The electrical resistivity survey involved vertical electrical sounding (VES) within the study area using Direct Data capture (DDC) Resistivity equipment. The Schlumberger electrode configuration was used, with maximum current electrode separation (AB/2) of 70m. The instrument, in this array measures vertical changes in ground resistivity with depth. This is the preferred way to locate vertical layers and aquifers thicknesses. The principle of the resistivity methods is that an electric current is passed into the ground through two current electrodes and the resulting potential difference is measured across two potential electrodes. The resulting potential difference to the current is displayed by the digital resistivity equipment as a resistance. The electrode spacing of 70m is progressively increased, keeping the center point of the electrode array fixed. At small electrode spacing, the apparent resistivity is nearly the resistivity of the surface material, but as the current electrodes spacing increase the current penetrates deeper within the subsurface and so the apparent resistivity reflects the resistivity of the deeper layers as well. The apparent resistivity values are obtained by multiplying the measured resistance with an appropriate geometric factor. The generated resistivity curves from the field measurements were first interpreted manually using curve matching and then completed using computer iteration software (IPI2WIN). Schlumberger electrode array is as shown in the Figure 4. The electrodes are arranged such that the distance AB between the current electrodes is greater or equal to five times the distance MN, between the potential electrodes. The potential electrodes are fixed about the data station in which the current electrodes are spread until the required maximum separation is attained.

For the Schlumberger electrode configuration,

$$\rho_a = \frac{\pi (L^2 - x^2)^2}{2l (L^2 + x^2)} \cdot \frac{\Delta V}{I} \tag{1}$$

Where x is the separation of the mid-points of the potential and current electrodes.

When used symmetrically,

$$x = 0, \text{ so } \rho_a = \frac{\pi L^2 \Delta V}{2l I} \tag{2}$$

$$\rho_a = \frac{\pi RL^2}{2l} \tag{3}$$

Equation (3) is the apparent resistivity for Schlumberger electrode array

Figure 4: The Schlumberger Electrode Configuration

- AB = 2L
- MN = 2l
- AB ≥ 5MN

3.0 Results and Discussions

The sounding curves (Figure 4a-d) obtained from the interpretation of the field resistivity data in the study revealed that the resistivity ranges between (18.9 – 7521 Ωm), thickness ranges between (0.5 – 11.73 m) and depth ranges between (0.5 – 56.3 m). The lithological units composed of the topsoil, laterite, clayey sand, weathered basement, basement and fresh bedrock. IPI2win program interpretation procedures correlated with the data obtained from the study area. The circles represent the measured data; red line represents the calculated data and blue line represents the interpreted resistivity section as shown in Figure 5a-d. The table in the right- hand side represents the values of interpreted resistivity, thickness, depth, and altitude of different geoelectrical layers. The modelled resist curves selected and presented are representatives of the many generated from the study based on the number of rock layers (Figure 4).

3.1 VES Curves Classification and Interpretations

The VES curve types obtained in the study area are the QHA, HA, KH, A and the KHA ranging from 5-6 layers. The curves are characterized by different lithologic units with their corresponding resistivity and thickness values (Figure 4a-d) which include the topsoil, laterite, clayey sand, weathered basement, basement and fresh bedrock with resistivities and thickness ranging from 72.4-753 Ωm with thickness 0.5- 2.05 m, 74.9-911 Ωm with thickness of 0.983 -3.54 m, 18.9-406 Ωm with thickness of about 3.07-19.6 m , 21.7-379 Ωm ; thickness of 5.3-44.5 m, 92.9-7521 Ωm ; thickness of about 11.4 -87.4m and 70.5 to 70798 Ωm with an indefinite thickness. The HA-type curve is characterized by five layers namely; topsoil, laterite, clayey sand, weathered basement, basement and fresh bedrock. The KH and KHA curves delineated six lithologic units which comprises the topsoil, laterite, clayey sand, weathered basement, basement and fresh bedrock. Four lithologic sequences (topsoil, laterite, weathered basement, basement and fresh bedrock) were observed on the QHA and KHA-type curves. Among all the lithologic units identified in the study area, only the weathered basement and the basement are categorized as the aquiferous layers. VES 1, 5, 7 and 10 contain these type of aquifers which are of hydrogeologic significance. This corroborated the works of [3] [12] who have shown that weathered layers within the hard rocks terrain like this study area may be regarded as good groundwater potential zones. Although, the resistivities (10 – 80 Ωm) of the weathered layers identified in this study suggests high clay to sand ratio, depicting low aquifer permeability. It is expected that areas with thickness greater than 25 m as seen in VES 1, 5, 7 and 10 (Table 1) have weathered layers which could be considered satisfactory for groundwater development. However, the basement usually possesses good groundwater potential due to enhanced porosity especially when its thickness is greater than 10 m [13]. Details of the geoelectric parameters with their lithologic sequences and their subsurface implications are presented in Table 1 below respectively.

Figure 5a: Modeled resist curve of VES1.

Figure 5b: Modeled resist curve of VES 2.

Figure 5c: Modeled resist curve of VES3.

Figure 5d: Modeled resist curve of VES4.

Table 1: Summary of Geoelectric Parameters Obtained from the Study Area

Ves no	Curve types	Layer	Resistivity range (Ohm-m)	Thickness range (m)	Lithology
1	QHA	1	133	1.67	Topsoil
		2	113	1.38	Laterite
		3	18.9	11.9	Clayey sand
		4	38.9	9.7	Weather Basement
		5	190	52.2	Basement
		6	1554	Not detected	Fresh Basement
2	QHA	1	134	2.05	Topsoil
		2	118	1.91	Laterite
		3	35.3	10.1	Clayey sand
		4	35.2	6.13	Basement
		5	5385	Not detected	Fresh Basement
3	HA	1	72.4	1.02	Topsoil
		2	74.9	1.29	Laterite
		3	44.6	8.33	Clayey sand
		4	60.1	8.18	Basement
		5	42.35	Not detected	Fresh Basement
4	AH	1	753	0.5	Topsoil
		2	519	1.2	Laterite
		3	215	7.79	Clayey sand
		4	90.9	6.8	Weather Basement
		5	126	11.4	Basement
		6	1268	Not detected	Fresh Basement
5	QA	1	193	0.893	Topsoil
		2	75.1	2.03	Laterite
		3	62.9	7.38	Clayey sand
		4	362	44.5	Basement
		5	44.5	Not detected	Fresh Basement
6	KH	1	103	0.808	Topsoil
		2	122	2.27	Laterite
		3	42.6	19.6	Clayey sand
		4	53.9	5.31	Weather Basement
		5	132	22.2	Basement
		6	1899	Not detected	Fresh Basement
7	QQH	1	184	1.52	Topsoil
		2	131	3.54	Laterite
		3	191	8.44	Clayey sand
		4	21.7	6.53	Weather Basement
		5	92.9	56.3	Basement
		6	2512	Not detected	Fresh Basement
8	HA	1	188	1	Topsoil
		2	224	1.68	Laterite
		3	258	3.57	Clayey sand
		4	232	19.9	Basement
		5	7521	Not detected	Fresh Basement
9	HA	1	346	0.748	Topsoil
		2	301	1.13	Laterite
		3	359	3.07	Clayey sand
		4	379	10.6	Weather Basement
		5	632	26	Basement
		6	70798	Not detected	Fresh Basement
10	KHA	1	643	1	Topsoil
		2	911	0.983	Laterite
		3	406	5.23	Clayey sand
		4	134	44	Weather Basement
		5	688	87.4	Basement
		6	70.5	Not detected	Fresh Basement

Goelectric Sections

VES results show that the study area is underlain by four to six distinct goelectric layers Fig (4a-d). Interpretation of the goelectric layers to their corresponding geologic unit was guided by lithologic units obtained from study the area. The typical sounding curves were used to generate the goelectric parameters presented in (Table 1). Goelectric sections were constructed based on the goelectric parameters. The top soil extends southwesterly of VES 1, 5, 6, and VES 10. The top soil is underlain by a sandy clay layer. The curves are characterized by lithologic units (Figure 5a-d) with their corresponding resistivity and thickness values which include the topsoil, laterite, clayey sand, weathered basement, basement and fresh bedrock with resistivities and

thickness ranging from 72.4-753 Ωm with thickness 0.5- 2.05 m, 74.9-911 Ωm with thickness of 0.983 -3.54 m, 18.9-406 Ωm with thickness of about 3.07-19.6 m , 21.7-379 Ωm ; thickness of 5.3-44.5 m, 92.9-7521 Ωm ; thickness of about 11.4 -87.4m and 70.5 to 70798 Ωm with an indefinite thickness. The possible water bearing zone was located around the VES 1, 3, and 10 where a thick overburden overlying the weathered zone made up of basement depression Interestingly, thick overburden materials are clay which can serve as a natural filter for the underground water. In the VES 2 and 5, no potential aquifer was identified as the moderately thick overburden material unconformable overlies the fresh basement ridge.

Figure 6: Goelectric section inferred from the VES curves

Overburden Thickness Map

The overburden thickness map (Figure 7) shows that the overburden thickness of the area varies

from 0.6 to 2m as shown in Figure 7. The result agrees with [14] which reported a range of 1.0-79.9 m as the range of overburden thickness that is obtainable within a basement complex. The

deductions of [15] and [2] that a minimum overburden thickness of 25 m is required for viable groundwater abstraction within the basement complex, which agrees with the results from this study to have limited groundwater potential. On the other hand, zones identified

having overburden thickness ≥ 25 m are considered to have strong appeal for groundwater development as such zone covers about 70 % of the entire study area.

Figure 7: Overburden Thickness Map

Groundwater Potential Evaluation

The groundwater potential evaluation of the area was derived from the combination of the aquifer resistivity and thickness parameters. The good groundwater potential zones coincide with areas characterized by depressions while zones with poor groundwater potential correspond to areas associated with basement ridges [3], [17]. The hydrogeologic importance of the basement depressions identified on the basement overburden thickness map (Figure 7) corroborated

the deductions from the groundwater map Figure 8. The aquifer resistivity and thickness parameters were synthesized and integrated for elucidating the groundwater potential of the area which was eventually used in rating it into low and moderate potential zones. The areas that falls within the reddish/yellowish/greenish/bluish colouration on Figure 8 are designated as poor groundwater potential zones while the pinkish colour band are regarded as good zones for groundwater development.

Figure 8: Groundwater Potential Map

4.0 Conclusion

Ten VES field data were carried out to determine the subsurface layer parameters in delineating geoelectric layers of the study area to give an insight into its groundwater potential. The survey involves Schlumberger electrode configuration with a maximum potential electrode spread (AB/2) of 70 m. Four to six geoelectric layers were delineated with QHA, QHA, HA, AH, QA, KH, QQH, A, HA, and KHA curve types identified. The interpreted geo-electric data displayed the variation of aquifer parameters and that of the Dar Zarrouk parameters. It was observed from the study that 70% of the study area falls within the low water bearing potential, 10% moderate and 20% were very low. It can be concluded that the groundwater potential of the area is generally low. It is recommended that geophysical investigations involving very low frequency electromagnetic (VLF-EM), magnetics and seismic refraction be carried out as a reconnaissance study to corroborate the results of this research.

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